

VARIOUS MANIFESTATIONS OF PERIODONTAL HYPERPLASIA IN CHILDREN

Mo'minov Mirzobek Mubinovich¹

1st year student

¹Bukhara State medical institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Email: mirikjan3@gmailcom

Raupov Doniyor Rahmon o'gli²

1st year student

²Bukhara State medical institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Email: raupovdonier14@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353272>

Hypertrophic gingivitis is a chronic inflammatory process of the gums, accompanied by proliferative phenomena. In foreign literature, the term was previously widely used to refer to this disease.

"Gingival hyperplasia". Both terms are acceptable for use, as they reflect varieties of the pathoanatomical process. Pathologically, hypertrophy is the overgrowth of tissue as a result of an increase in cell size, while hyperplasia is the overgrowth of tissue as a result of an increase in the number of cells. From our point of view, the term "hyperplasia" is more universal, as it combines both "inflammatory processes in the gums", and "growths of a tumor and drug nature, and hereditary diseases. To date, the recognized designations of this condition in foreign literature are such names as "gingival enlargement" and "gingival overgrowth", which can be translated as "gingival enlargement" and "gingival growth".

The causes of gingival hyperplasia are varied and may be associated with the action of local and systemic factors. Localized gingival hypertrophy develops with crowding of teeth, trauma of the mucous membrane with overhanging fillings, clasps, artificial crowns, elements of the bracket system, malocclusion and oral breathing are of some importance (Fig. 1, 2).

A generalized process occurs in adolescents in the puberty period, with endocrine diseases, blood diseases (leukemic reticulosis, myeloid leukemia), taking certain medications, etc.

Gingival growth during puberty occurs in boys and girls in places of greatest plaque accumulation. Often, the lesion is most pronounced on the vestibular surface of the teeth and is practically absent on the oral surface, which is associated with the cleansing effect of the tongue and the food bolus during eating (Fig. 3). After the completion of puberty, the gingival growth undergoes spontaneous reduction, but does not disappear completely while maintaining

poor oral hygiene. The main mechanism of development of juvenile gingival hyperplasia is associated with an increase in the reactivity of periodontal tissues due to the formation of new vascular networks against the background of hormonal imbalance. At the same time, a vicious circle is formed - the more hypertrophied and edematous the gum, the more difficult it is for the patient to brush his teeth. Unsatisfactory oral hygiene and the accumulation of plaque lead to an even stronger inflammatory reaction of periodontal tissues and increased gum edema, conditions are created for intensive development and penetration into the underlying tissues of anaerobic periodontopathogenic microorganisms. Often it is the pubertal period with the development of gingival hyperplasia that becomes the impetus for the manifestation of hereditary predisposition and triggers the development of genetically determined aggressive forms of periodontitis [3].

Other factors leading to inflammation periodontal overreaction include deficiency vitamin C, plasma cell infiltration. In leukemia, the connective tissue of the gums is impregnated with a dense mass of proliferating immature leukocytes, the type of which depends on the type of blood disease. Despite the fact that the overgrown gum is quite dense, it is easily vulnerable, prone to bleeding and ulceration even with the slightest damage. Systemic disorders in which generalized gingival hyperplasia may occur include blood diseases such as thrombocytopathy and thrombocytopenia (Fig. 4), as well as immunologically caused diseases with the formation of specific granulomas in tissues (Wegener's granulomatosis, sarcoidosis) [11].

Generalized gingival hyperplasia may develop as a result of long-term use of drugs (Fig. 5, 6). In more than 50% of cases, hyperplasia develops when taking the anticonvulsant difenin, which is still widely used in the treatment of epilepsy and convulsive syndromes in children. Another drug that causes the development of gingival hyperplasia in more than 70% of children is the immunosuppressant cyclosporine A (in adults, this complication occurs only in 30% of cases when taking the drug). This drug is used in the treatment of many diseases with an "autoimmune" component, and is also prescribed for life after organ transplantation. Researchers note that taking cyclosporin A is accompanied by a characteristic lobulation of the gums, as well as significantly more edema and bleeding than when taking diphenin, when the growths are of a fibrous nature [10]. Less commonly, gingival growth is recorded while taking calcium channel blockers in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases (nifedipine, diltiazem, verapamil, less often amlodipine, etc.).

Figure 1. Hypertrophy of the interdental papillae in crowded teeth

Figure 2. Localized hypertrophic gingivitis in the area of 2.2 teeth

Figure 3. Generalized juvenile hypertrophic gingivitis

Figure 4. Localized gingival hyperplasia in a 16-year-old girl with thrombocytopeny

These drugs are used much less frequently in children, however, the development of severe gingival hyperplasia has been described with the simultaneous use of cyclosporine (one of the complications of which is the development of arterial hyperlipidosis). A relatively common neoplasm from the surface epithelium in the oral cavity is squamous papilloma. It is located usually on the site of attached gums and "characterized by exophytic growth, the surface has the appearance of a cauliflower and is "covered with characteristic outgrowths (Fig.5, 6). Usually located on a stalk. Infection with the human papillomavirus plays a large role in the appearance of a tumor, although during examination it is not always detected. Histologically, the tumor is a proliferation of the spiny layer of the epithelium with hyperkeratosis. Treatment is surgical excision of the formation along with the "base of tension") and calcium channel blockers. The degree of gingival hypertrophy is directly proportional to the dose of the drug and the duration of its administration. Gingival growth is associated with increased activity of connective tissue fibroblasts and 7. Papilloma of the gums in the region of the lateral incisor of the upper jaw Fig . five. Squamous cell papillomatosis of the gums in the area of 1.1 tooth in a 9-year-old girl with an excess amount of extracellular collagen, although the mechanisms of this process remain unclear until the end [6, 8]. It should be noted that gingival hyperplasia develops most strongly with the combined action of drugs on one side and a microbial plaque on the other.

Sometimes the cause of hypertrophic growths of the gums cannot be found, but this is rather due to the "incomplete collection of anamnesis" and the imperfection of diagnostic methods.

The clinic of the disease is characteristic. In the edematous form, patients complain of gum growth, itching, bleeding, pain during meals, bad breath. Characterized by the formation of gingival pockets, an abundance of soft and pigmented plaque on the teeth. Gingival papillae are brightly hyperemic, edematous, bleed on palpation. The

fibrous form proceeds benignly. The patient complains about the unusual appearance and shape of the gums. Gingival papillae of normal color, do not bleed. Additional research methods make it possible to identify the inflammatory process of the mucous membrane of varying degrees of intensity.

Figure 5. Papilloma of the gums in the region of the lateral incisor of the upper jaw

Figure 8. Squamous cell papillomatosis of the gums in the area of 1.1 tooth in a 9-year-old girl

Differential diagnosis is carried out with gingival fibromatosis, various forms of epulis. A relatively common neoplasm in the oral cavity from the surface epithelium is squamous papilloma. It is usually located in the area of the attached gum and is characterized by exophytic growth, the surface looks like a cauliflower and is covered with characteristic outgrowths (Fig. 5, 6). Usually located on the leg. Infection with the human papillomavirus plays an important role in the appearance of a tumor, although it is not always detected during examination. Histologically, the tumor is a proliferation of the spinous layer of the epithelium with hyperkeratosis. Treatment is surgical excision of the formation along with the base. Gingival fibromatosis is a rare hereditary disease and is characterized by diffuse or limited hypertrophy of the interdental papillae, gingival margin and alveolar gingiva. The disease can develop independently or be part of hereditary syndromes (Cross, Leybend, Cowden, Rutherford, etc.). It occurs in adolescents and young people, mainly in girls.

The process is more pronounced from the vestibular side. Fibrous growths of the gums of a pale pink color, dense, painless, do not bleed, sometimes slow down teething. The lesion may take the form of symmetrical olive-shaped fibromas, localizing more on the oral surface of the alveolar processes of the jaws in the region of the molars. Diagnosis is made on the basis of history and clinical examination, supplemented by biopsy and histological examination. Surgical treatment. The use of modern electrocoagulators facilitates gingivectomy, provides instant hemostasis, but requires certain skills from the surgeon to correctly form the future soft tissue contour of the attached and marginal gingiva, as well as to prevent damage to the underlying bone tissue.

Epulis is another frequent hyperplastic process in periodontal tissues in children. This is a benign tumor-like formation that occurs in places of chronic irritation. The disease is common, characterized by limited growth of the gums in the region of the incisors, canines or small molars.

The tumor grows on a wide rounded stalk and has a mushroom shape. The tumor develops only next to the "teeth", therefore it is conventionally classified as a "series of odontogenic". There are angiomatous, fibrous and giant cell epulis. Angiomatous epulis is characterized by a soft texture, a large number of blood vessels with cavities. In this case, the tumor has a bluish-purple color and is characterized by progressive growth. Injury to the neoplasm may cause bleeding. Fibrous epulis of a denser consistency, often of a pale pink color. In the initial stage, the bone is not changed, as the tumor grows into the periodontium, foci of destruction appear in the alveolar process, and pathological tooth mobility develops. Giant cell epulis is a peripheral form of osteoblastoclastoma, which proceeds with destruction of the bone of the alveolar process, resorption of the roots of the teeth.

Excision of the epulis is carried out at its base on the alveolar process with subsequent diathermocoagulation or cryodestruction of the growth zone in the periodontium (Fig. 15-18). In case of peripheral osteoblastoclastoma, the alveolar process is resected together with the teeth located in the tumor zone.

Vinogradova T.F. notes that in "children in the period of immaturity of the hormonal genital area, it is necessary to resort to" surgical methods with "great caution, since they can lead to destruction of the periodontal ligament, the occurrence of deeper periodontal lesions and relapses of gingival hypertrophy [2]. It is also necessary to consult a specialist regarding the use of antibiotics and steroid hormones and the elimination of symptoms of arterial hypertension when planning a surgical intervention in patients with immunosuppression while taking cyclosporine A [8].

Thus, hyperplastic processes in periodontal tissues in children have a different etio-pathogenetic nature. The action of systemic factors is exacerbated by poor oral hygiene. A large number of conservative and surgical methods of treatment have been proposed, the competent use of which will allow achieving good results and preventing the development of destructive periodontal lesions in the future.

References:

1. Myers B.D., Newton L. Cyclosporine -induced chronic nephropathy: An obliterative microvascular renal injury. // J. Am. Soc. Nephrol. - 1991. - Vol.2. - P.45-52.

2. Rees T .D . Editor: Disorders affecting the periodontium, Peri- odontol 200021:45, 1999.
3. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 59-65.
4. Djalilova, Z. O. (2021). Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3), 391-397.
5. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). Physical activity and its impact on human health and longevity. Достижения науки и образования, (2 (82)), 120-126.
6. Obidovna, D. Z., & Denis, S. (2021). Formulas of speech etiquette in a gender-engineered communication strategy. Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences, 2(6), 5-11.
7. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics. Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture, 2(2), 22-26.
8. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). Speech Behavior and its Gender Specificity on the Basis of the Main English Language Variants. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 22, 199-205.
9. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue. Gender issues, 7(6).
10. JALILOVA, Z. O. (2021, March). ON THE FORMATION OF THE LANGUAGE OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE IN THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 18-22).
11. Jalilova, Z. O. (2020). Concerning the issue of terms, having a place with various morphological classes (in view of the example of the terminological arrangement of social action). Новый день в медицине, (4), 501-503.
12. Djalilova, Z. O., Juraev, S. S., & Kosimov, S. M. (2021). LATIN AS A PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE OF MEDICAL WORKERS. Международный научно-практический электронный журнал «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА». Выпуск № 23 (том 1)(апрель, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.04. 2021., 79.
13. Джалилова, З. О., Хасанов, К. А., & Султонов, А. А. (2021). Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане. Молодой ученый, (26), 377-379.
14. Dzhalilova, Z. O. (2021). The Latin language's international status. Молодой ученый, (41), 32-34.

15. Dzhaliilova, Z. O., & Mirfajziev, K. (2021). Latin as the language of medicine. Молодой ученый, (41), 35-37.
16. Dzhaliilova, Z. O., Izomova, S. G., & Ahmedova, G. A. (2021). Intercultural communication and the Latin language. Молодой ученый, (24), 398-400.
17. Dzhaliilova, Z. O. (2021). History of formation of Latin language. Молодой ученый, (41), 34-35.
18. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER SPEECH BEHAVIOR IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SOCIO-LINGUISTIC FACTOR. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(6), 190-198.
19. Dzhaliilova, Z. O., Hajdarova, N. S., & Tashpulatova, N. A. (2021). Latin in the Contemporary World. Молодой ученый, (24), 400-402.
20. Djalilova, Z. (2022). POLITENESS IN WOMEN'S DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Academic research in modern science, 1(11), 29-34.
21. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 3(06), 53-64.
22. Джалилова, З. (2022). РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ МАКСИМ ВЕЖЛИВОСТИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ДИАЛОГАХ. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(21), 22-33.
23. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). A Speech Etiquette Formula for the Gender Communication Strategy. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 44-50.
24. Jo'rayev, S., & Djalilova, Z. (2022). NEUROLOGICAL STATUS OF CHILDREN WITH INTRAUTERINE DEVELOPMENTAL DELAY.
25. Djalilova, Z. (2022). DISCURSIVE ELEMENTS AND THE CATEGORY OF POLITENESS. Academic research in modern science, 1(12), 8-14.
26. Джалилова, З. О. (2022). НУТҚ ҲАРАКАТЛАРИДА ХУШМУОМАЛАЛИКНИНГ ГЕНДЕР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 5(5).
27. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF MALE AND FEMALE ORAL SPEECH IN MODERN ENGLISH. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 2(10), 14-21.
28. Jo'rayev, S. (2022). FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA AND ITS TREATMENT IN CHILDREN. Академические исследования в современной науке, 1(17), 41-48.

29. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 3(6), 1-12.
30. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 59-65.
31. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF POLITENESS IN MODERN LINGUOPRAGMATICS: THE POLITENESS PRINCIPLE BY J. LEECH. International Journal of Pedagogics, 2(11), 15-20.
32. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2021). The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe. Central Asian Journal Of Social Sciences And History, 2(10), 10-14.
33. Zaynitdinovna, T. N. (2022). Lyrical Dialogue in Shakespeare's Poems as a Reflection of Renaissance Anthropocentrism and a Strong Personality. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 21, 120-125.
34. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). The Problem of "A Strong Personality" in Shakespeare's Dramas: Richard III and Macbeth. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 20, 7-10.
35. Ташева, Н. З. (2022). КРИСТОФЕР МАРЛОУ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ): ТАМЕРЛЕН ВЕЛИКИЙ КАК ТИП ЛИЧНОСТИ ВОСТОЧНОГО ПРАВИТЕЛЯ. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(2), 234-239.
36. Zayniddinovna, T. N., & Sharofiddinovich, S. S. (2021). General cultural and educational values of ancient-classic latin language. Central Asian Journal Of Theoretical & Applied Sciences, 2(5), 77-80.
37. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2021). The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY, 2 (10), 10-14.
38. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). THE CHARACTER OF STRONG PERSONALITY ACCORDINGLY WITH EASTERN THEMATICS IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S PLAY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 2(08), 9-14.
39. nafisa Zayniddinovna, T. (2022). Lexico-Semantic Word Production as a Way of Forming Theater Terminology of the English Language. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 144-150.
40. Khamrayeva, S. (2022). FEATURES OF MEDICAL EDUCATION AND THE ROLE OF THE UNIVERSITY TEACHER IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AT THE PRESENT STAGE. Models and methods in modern science, 1(16), 57-67.

41. Khamrayeva, S. (2022). THROMBOSIS OF THE CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES. Models and methods in modern science, 1(16), 72-77.

